

Spiny-tailed lizard from Mali: '*Uromastyx maliensis*'

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INTRODUCTION

The lizards of the genus *Uromastyx* are beautifully coloured, active, vegetarian lizards that have been imported in reasonable numbers over the last few years. Unfortunately, because of the irresponsible way these animals are being caught in their natural habitat (in large numbers), it is to be expected that their import will gradually decline in the future. This is a positive development, as it should never be because of the pet trade or hobbies that populations of animals in the wild are becoming endangered. In order to maintain these animals in captivity it is absolutely essential to breed them. Until recently *Uromastyx* were rarely, if ever, bred in captivity. Several reports of failed breeding attempts in the past exist e.g., KRAALINGEN, 1980 and UYTTERSCHOUT, 1993. More recently, people are becoming more and more successful at breeding these lizards and Blijdorp Zoo, for example, is consistently breeding them (ZWARTEPOORTE, 1994) although they recently had to replace their breeding group because of old age (Zwartepoorte, pers. com.). As well, there are more and more hobbyists that are breeding these beautiful lizards (Briegoos, pers. comm.; WILMS & LÖHR, 1996).

DISTRIBUTION RANGE

The distribution range of *Uromastyx* extends from northern Africa (Morocco, Algeria and Tunisia), through Egypt, Sudan and the Arabian Peninsula to Asia Minor, Pakistan and western India. The animals live in dry rocky areas with a substratum that allows them to excavate their burrows (WILMS, 1995). It is clear that with such a large distribution range a relatively large number of species and subspecies are described. Wilms recognises nine species; with the additional form from Mali described here, the total number of species is currently considered to be ten. Apart from these ten species, a large number of subspecies have also been described, and it is to be expected that with the modern methods of genetic research the number of species and subspecies will increase. This paper is about the Mali *Uromastyx*. This species inhabits the dry sandy areas in the swamps of Mali (south-west of Timbuktu). Although a swampy area seems to be a highly unusual habitat for *Uromastyx*, the animal is only found there in the dry sand dunes.

A young '*Uromastyx maliensis*'.

Photo: G. Hofstra

CLIMATE

The following graph shows the climatic data of Timbuktu. This climate can be characterised as dry and hot, with clear differences between the seasons and a moderate difference between day- and night-time temperatures (approximately 8°C).

Average temperature and precipitation in Timbuktu (Mali).

Portrait of a male '*Uromastix maliensis*'.

Photo: G. Hofstra

STATUS

Currently, this form is generally considered a separate species; this is mainly based on the large (physical) distance between the Mali population and the known distribution range of *Uromastix acanthinura* (JOGER & LAMBERT, 1996). Furthermore, the sexual dimorphisms of the Mali form, and the more delicate scutellation of the latter back up the species status. In the original research paper a reference is made to a difference in the protein contents of the blood plasma. Unfortunately, information is missing concerning the number of animals tested and the variance within the populations. Without that sort of information, there is insufficient evidence to support this claim. (A person with blood type O is not placed in a separate subspecies either, even though their blood plasma protein characteristics are different). DNA research will most likely be able to clear this matter up, but to my knowledge this has not yet taken place.

In conclusion, I am of the opinion that the species status is currently only moderately convincing. For the sake of clarity I will therefore refer to this form as '*Uromastix maliensis*'.

Characteristics	' <i>U. maliensis</i> '	<i>U. a. geyri</i>	<i>U. a. acanthinura</i>
Enlarged scales on the flanks	absent	present	absent
Points near ear opening	weak	strong	weak
Relative tail length (% of snout-vent length)	55.7-69.4 (avg. 63.1) (n=13)	72.5-88.5 (avg. 80.9) (n=13)	52.1-67.7 (avg. 61.5) (n=13)
Number of tail rings	17-20 (avg. 18.6) (n=14)	20-23 (avg. 21.3) (n=16)	16-20 (avg. 18.5) (n=13)
Number of scale rows between eyes and lips	6-7 (n=5)	4-5 (n=6)	4-5 (n=6)
Number of scales between ear and apex of head ¹	31-43 (avg. 36.0) (n=14)	22-32 (avg. 25.7) (n=17)	24-31 (avg. 27.5) (n=13)
Number of scales between eye and ear ²	60-98 (avg. 76.6) (n=7)	40-63 (avg. 49.1) (n=12)	50-112 (avg. 72.1) (n=8)
Number of ventral scales	88-120 (avg. 97.7) (n=14)	70-111 (avg. 90.6) (n=16)	78-97 (avg. 84.0) (n=13)
Number of scales below fourth toe ³	16-20 (avg. 17.3) (n=14)	12-20 (avg. 16.3) (n=14)	11-17 (avg. 13.5) (n=10)
Scale counts: ¹ From the lower part of the ear opening below the lower jaw to the scale on the apex of the head. ² The product of two counts a. From the top of the ear to the nearest enlarged scale near the eye. b. Parallel to the ear at a distance of three scales from the ear opening from top down. ³ Below the fourth toe of the left foot from the tip to the point where the fourth toe joins the third toe.			

Table: Differences between '*U. maliensis*', *U. acanthinura geyri* and *U. a. acanthinura* (from: JOGER & LAMBERT, 1996).

DESCRIPTION

'*Uromastix maliensis*' is a relatively robust lizard. My largest adult male measures 35 cm (snout-vent + tail: 23+12 cm) and weighs about 600 gram. The males are more brightly coloured than the females. Males have delicate, bright yellow markings on the back, which contrast sharply with the otherwise pitch black background colour. In females the head and tail are usually brownish, as opposed to the black in males. In this species, the feet are usually yellow, although I have noticed in my animals that this yellow colour is not always permanent.

BEHAVIOUR

Uromastyx species, especially *U. hardwickii*, are known to live in groups, and are very territorial. In my experience males are very intolerant of each other, especially during the breeding season, and they cannot be kept together. The relationship between a male and a female may vary. I own one pair that never has any problems, and one pair that occasionally hisses at each other. Since this is usually the extent of their aggressive behaviour, it is not worth worrying about too much.

During the breeding season the male will approach the female, while bobbing on his front limbs in a very impressive way. Normally, the female will either try to walk away or turn herself on her back. In the first scenario, I have observed on several occasions that the male will follow the female into one of the burrows and drag her out by her tail. If the female turns on her back, the male will circle her several times while bobbing his head or even walk over her. This may work as a stimulant. Mating will only take place if the female is willing. After laying the eggs, the female is usually somewhat weakened, although she will fiercely defend the egg-laying site against the male, but also against other females. Under these circumstances it may be advisable to separate the male from the female temporarily until the female has regained her strength, especially in a small terrarium.

A striking phenomenon is that in a number of observations the female would excavate the hole in which she had laid the eggs just prior to hatching. Since I have only observed this in three instances, I don't yet feel that I can draw any conclusions from these observations. It does not appear to be essential for the survival of the young because they are excellent burrowers upon hatching. According to Zwartepoorte (pers. comm.) this behaviour has also been observed in *U. acanthinura*. In my opinion '*U. maliensis*' is more aggressive than *U. acanthinura*. While it sometimes is possible to keep several male *U. acanthinura* together in a large terrarium and still breed them (this was the old situation in Blijdorp Zoo), it is often necessary to separate the sexes of '*U. maliensis*' directly after the female lays her eggs. The female is so protective and intolerant that she will not let the male anywhere near the nest site. I should add that I have heard from other people that they were successful in keeping this species in groups (Koreman, pers. comm.).

My animals are very quiet and friendly towards people; they rarely flee, never bite, and eagerly accept food from your hand. They also show no signs of aggression towards smaller lizards of other species. I have kept them together with *Podarcis sicula* (which had to adjust their basking schedule) and have never had any problems. Also, a combination with *Pogona vitticeps* or a small species of agama from the Middle East has been successful (Briegoos, pers. comm.).

CARE IN THE TERRARIUM

Uromastyx species are active territorial lizards with a clear mating and introduction behaviour. It is obvious that these lizards can only be kept appropriately in a relatively large terrarium, starting with at least 0.8 m² of floor surface for a pair. Even though commercial breeding appears possible in a relatively small terrarium, I do not encourage this form of bio-industry, which appears to be gaining popularity, especially in the USA.

Looking at the distribution range of these animals, it is clear that they require relatively high environmental temperatures to thrive. However, the night-time temperature can be considerably lower than the daytime temperature. A basking spot where the temperature is raised to at least 45°C, with the aid of a (halogen) spotlight is absolutely essential for the well-being of these lizards. Temperatures much higher than that are still considered acceptable by these animals (even when the temperature underneath the spotlight reaches approximately 60°C, they still display basking behaviour). It is clear that such a high temperature should not prevail in the entire terrarium, and it is important that the animals can retreat to cooler places. An average temperature inside the terrarium of 30-33°C seems ideal to me, provided that a shelter is available where the temperature is substantially lower. Wilms (pers. comm.) reports that inside these shelters the temperature should remain above 25°C. Such a retreat is essential inside each terrarium, and the animals will use them every night. In my terrarium they are constructed out of pre-fab gyp rock blocks, which have the added advantage of absorbing a lot of water, leaving the relative humidity inside the shelter much higher than in the rest of the terrarium. Because of the high evaporation inside the shelter, the temperature is also reduced.

Apart from the climatic advantages, this material also makes a very solid construction that does not collapse easily. Since these animals burrow frequently, it is important that all constructions inside the terrarium are properly stabilised, so the animals do not hurt themselves if something collapses on top of them.

A decent ventilation system is important because of the strong heating and lighting. I work with a terrarium that has an open top (60% metal mosquito screen) and has the light fixtures (fluorescent tube lights) and heating (pressure lights 80-100 W) located on top of that. This has the added advantage that the animals can never be in direct contact with the electrical current, and it just looks nicer if there are no light bulbs visible inside the terrarium. One disadvantage of this method is that the distance between terraria stacked on top of each other needs to be fairly large, since there needs to be sufficient room for the electrical system, and sufficient ventilation should be guaranteed.

The terraria are completely constructed out of glass, have a bottom substrate of coarse sand and are decorated with large rocks and logs. I think that a lively decoration where one takes into account some sight barriers for the animals is essential for successfully keeping these lizards. These sight barriers ensure that animals can hide from each other within the confined space of a terrarium. It is also important that the animals can not see animals in other terraria.

The use of lava rock has led to the occurrence of small lesions that resulted in infections in some animals, most likely because of their sharp surface. I now use softer types of rock, and no more infections on the feet have occurred.

FOOD

Uromastyx species are primarily herbivores, although most animals if given a chance will take animal food as well. Their food will thus need to be mostly vegetable matter. Of course there are numerous different possibilities, but I would like to offer some specific advice.

Examples of suitable food are:

leafy vegetables such as dandelions, plantain, endives, cabbage (not too much) and other vegetables with a beneficial Ca/P content and poor in unwanted compounds like oxalic acid (which blocks the Ca intake); seeds (non-fat; I mainly use weed seeds for juveniles and pigeon food for adults, complemented with corn); fruits like tomatoes, apples, grapes (not too much) and carrots; insects such as moths, crickets, grasshoppers and morio worms; some adult males will even eat juvenile mice.

Some people who keep *Uromastyx* are of the opinion that it is preferable to offer them a larger share of the (vegetable) food in dry form. This would promote intestinal activity and lessen the chance of constipation, especially in juveniles (Gaal, pers. comm.). In spite of the fact that I offer my animals a lot of fresh vegetables, I have never experienced any problems with constipation. The vegetables I offer do have a much higher share of dry matter than, for example, endives (pers. obs.).

It is advisable to feed the animals grated carrots on a regular basis, since they contain lots of carotene. Lizards can process carotene into vitamin A, if needed, whereas a surplus of carotene is simply excreted. Carrots are therefore a relatively safe way to administer herbivores extra vitamin A although excess amounts can still be harmful.

Opinions differ about supplying animal food and I am very careful when providing it.

The hunting behaviour that my animals show when chasing crickets indicates, however, that in the wild a part of their diet consists of animal prey. On the other hand, examination of the dung of recently imported animals only revealed vegetable matter (beetle chelytra will often remain visible in the faeces).

Opinions differ on the matter of offering water. Personally, I always make sure that clean drinking water (enriched with calcium and vitamins) is available. I do have to admit that I never or very rarely see them drink (apart from some of the juveniles). Other people indicate that the animals obtain sufficient moisture from their food, or can satisfy their needs by drinking the water that is sprayed occasionally. Some people are of the opinion that placing a bowl of drinking water in the terrarium can be dangerous for the animals. I definitely do not agree with that since I have never experienced any negative effects by having water in a terrarium. The whole discussion on moisture and water is most likely started by the observation that *Uromastyx* often leaves fresh food to dry for a while before eating it, resulting in the fact that many wild caught animals die from dehydration. Also, these animals are thought to absorb moisture through their skin (Wilms, pers. comm.), which is a remarkable thought, considering these animals live in deserts. One thing that is clear, however, is that there exists a subtle equilibrium between the different ways these lizards can absorb water and care should be taken.

HIBERNATION

In order to successfully breed most *Uromastyx* species, I believe that a hibernation period is essential. I keep my animals on a lighting schedule attuned to the situation at 35 degrees latitude (14-hour days during the summer and in the winter 8-hour days). With this schedule, and with the temperature effects caused by the lower outside temperature, the animals become noticeably less active around mid-October, and stay inside their (artificial) shelters for longer periods. Around mid-November to early December they hardly leave their shelters anymore. This is when I turn off the heat save for a small spot light that the animals can still use to bask. The temperature inside my reptile room drops to around 18-20°C during the day, and a few degrees lower at night. The fluorescent tube lights stay on during the entire hibernation period. The animals are frequently offered clean water, but no food. The lizards do not go through a complete hibernation since they occasionally emerge from their burrows to bask for a short period of time, however, they do not eat at all during this time. It is striking that the males are occasionally active, and show themselves more often than the females, although the low number of observations does not permit drawing any firm conclusions.

During February-March the heat is turned back on again, and the animals are fed.

When looking at the climatic data, it is clear that the cooling that I just described is much more pronounced than that which prevails in the animal's natural habitat. However, since the animals are kept together with some more northerly species that do need this intense hibernation, I have no choice but to put them through it. However, the animals do not seem to suffer from any deleterious effects.

During hibernation, the animals' body weights decrease only slightly, if at all, and they are in great shape directly after. One advantage of this hibernation is that it attunes the sexual cycles of both the male and the female, and possibly even more important is the actual stimulus for reproduction which is triggered by hibernating.

CALCIUM, VITAMINS, AND UV

As a rule I give my animals the following vitamin and mineral supplements: drinking water: 12,000 i.u./litre D₃ (use a water-soluble supplement) and calcium lactate 2 g/litre. (Note: 1 µg D₃=40 i.u.) This is the mixture I use for my reptiles in all their drinking water and the water that I spray. Disadvantages of this mixture are that water droplets on the windows leave a white residue when they dry up (so I need to clean the windows regularly), and calcium lactate is a good substrate for micro-organisms. You will need to refresh the drinking water frequently, and disinfect the water bowls. Three times a week I refresh the drinking water, and thoroughly clean and disinfect the bowls by washing them in a bleach/soap solution.

Vegetable matter is enriched with Korvimin or Gistocal: approximately 0.25 gram per 100 gram food. Korvimin is added once a week and Gistocal five times per week. Six times a week the animals receive plant matter for food. In addition, small amounts of sepia are present inside the terraria for whenever the animals may want it.

I believe that when the animals are breeding additional calcium and extra vitamin D₃ is essential. I also feel that intensive UV radiation is critical for a successful breeding attempt.

I realise that I am offering my animals relatively large doses of calcium and vitamins, in spite of the fact that the food that I offer them naturally contains lots of calcium in a very healthy Ca/P. However, my animals keep nibbling at the gyp rock blocks that I used for constructing their shelters, and I interpret this as a craving for calcium.

With regards to vitamin D₃, I fear that radiation with UV alone will be insufficient, and I have chosen to use a dosage that, according to IN DEN BOSCH (1996), is considered safe for West-Palearctic lizards, (and should therefore also be safe for *Uromastyx*). I supplement this with UV radiation to prevent possible deficiencies.

DISEASES

Wild caught *Uromastyx* are often heavily infected with different kinds of nematodes, which may or may not lead to disease or weight loss. Since the chances of infection under terrarium conditions are much higher, it is advisable to keep the nematode burden to a minimum. Furthermore, the animals are very susceptible to bacterial infections. Fortunately, since the animals inhabit a dry terrarium it is relatively easy to keep the chances of infections to a minimum.

Many micro-organisms will not be able to survive these conditions. It is still very important to clean out faeces on a daily basis and to clean the drinking bowls regularly.

Another problem is the occurrence of growths on the lips and tail. The growths on the lips appear like a whitish thickening that is reminiscent of poor moulting. When the tail is affected, this only clears up after ecdysis, or when several scales at the infected area are removed. Instead of new skin, the spot is covered by a whitish, hard-looking mass, reminiscent of chalk. The infection on the lips is instantly recognised as a whitish thickening covering healthy-looking scales. The reasons for these infections are not completely clear to me. This infection appears only moderately contagious, and often animals inhabiting the same terrarium will remain clear of symptoms for many years. The infection appears most similar to "scaly legs", a disease found in chickens. In those animals, the infection is caused by a mite (*Cnemidocoptes mutans*) (see BRUNEEL, 2000). I have had reasonable success fighting this disease by treating my animals externally with the disinfectant medicanol (70% alcohol, 0.5% chlorine hexidine) combined with a greasy anti-fungal cream (Fungivet). If the disease is truly caused by a mite, the success of the latter cream lies only in its consistency. I originally started using this cream because I thought the disease was fungus-based. However, microscopic examination did not reveal any of the characteristic mycelia.

The treatment mentioned here is not completely effective. While the infected areas can be removed successfully, the symptoms usually return within several months. Henk Zwartepoorte (pers. comm.) has recently indicated that his animals benefited greatly from treatment with the wide-spectrum antibiotic Doxycycline, administered orally for ten days. A 275 g male was given 0.25 ml/dzy.

BREEDING

After the temperature is increased, the animals become active again and quickly resume eating. Two to three weeks after turning on the heat the males start courting and mating will start to take place. The mating behaviour is very similar to that described for *U. acanthinura* by ZWARTEPOORTE (1994), including the fact that they circle the female while head-bobbing and the typical behaviour in which the female that is not ready to mate will turn on her back. On several occasions I have seen the male attempt to turn the female over again despite her initial aversion, or observed the male dragging the female out of a burrow by her tail to mate with her. Fortunately, it is not always rape, and normal mating will take place as well.

After a successful mating, the female will grow very big and will bask more than normal. At this point in time the relationship between the male and female is still all right.

Six to eight weeks after mating, depending on the size of the female, approximately 25 eggs are laid. For the egg-laying site I use humid river sand that is held in place by some bricks, and covered with a roof tile. Humid river sand can be compacted thoroughly, allowing the animals to burrow in it without the danger of the tunnels collapsing. Sometimes, when the oviposition takes too long, I start excavating a burrow for them.

After oviposition not much is left of the female; the joint total weight of the eggs is more than the body weight of the female. Additional care is needed to ensure that the female does not develop any problems. To complicate matters, females defend their nesting site after oviposition. Therefore, it may be smart to temporarily place the male in a separate terrarium.

I incubate the eggs in a commercial Jaeger type FB 80 Rep incubator. For incubation medium I use vermiculite mixed 1:1 with water (so 100 gram of vermiculite of grain size 1-3 is mixed with 100 gram water). In literature, a much drier substrate is indicated, but in my experience a drier substrate causes the eggs to collapse. With said mixture, I have had no problems with eggs collapsing, nor do I lose eggs because of fungal infections. I am also of the opinion that eggs that develop fungal infections were not fine to begin with.

At an incubation temperature of 32°C, my animal's eggs hatched after 87 to 126 days. This incubation period is extremely long when compared with values in the literature, and experiences of other breeders. I do not know what causes this phenomenon, but the juveniles look well developed and healthy.

I expect that in *Uromastyx* species the gender of the offspring is determined by the incubation temperature (HOFSTRA, 1998). In the future I want to incubate the eggs at different temperatures, for example 29 and 31°C, and then monitor the juveniles for several years to determine their gender.

Below is a list of the reproductive data of my animals for 1998, with the only difference in care being the presence of an UV-light (ZooMed 5.0- minimum distance between the light and the animals was about 30 cm and it was used the entire day).

In January 2000 I started using my new reptile room, which gives me the opportunity to use Osram Ultra Vitalux 300 W lights for one hour a day (minimum distance between light and animals is 45-50 cm). I have obtained very good results using these lights.

Loss late in incubation means that the juvenile died just before hatching. In 1998, I manually opened several eggs of the clutch of pair #2; this was not very successful. The loss of the eggs of pair #1 only involves the eggs that collapsed approximately one month before the projected hatching date. The young was still alive, but apparently lacked the strength to open the egg and ended up dying around the time that the other young hatched. Helping the young by manually opening the eggs is not successful since juveniles with a very large yolk residue do not survive. In 1999, two out of the four young suffered from small skeletal malformations; in one case two toes were fused, and in another one of the hind feet was missing. I suspect that the high incubation temperature caused this. It is striking that there is such a big difference in incubation period, while the eggs are all offered the same environmental conditions. I think this can be explained by the strength of the young inside the eggs, although I have to admit to not seeing any visible difference in vitality once they are hatched.

Pair	Data		Incubation period	Incubation temperature (°C)	Number of eggs	Number of young	Loss of eggs		UV
	Clutch	Hatched					Early	Late	
1	08-06-98	02-10-98	119	31	16	10	3	3	ZooMed 5.0
2	11-05-98	07-09-98	116	31	22	2	6	14	none
2	17-05-99	04-09-99	110	32	12	4	6	2	UltraVitalux (incidentally)
1	26-05-00	21-08-00	87	31	15	13	2	0	UltraVitalux
2	07-05-00	02-08-00	87	31	25	24	1	0	UltraVitalux

Summary clutches '*Uromastix maliensis*'.

A '*Uromastix maliensis*' hatches.

Photo: G. Hofstra

REARING THE YOUNG

Juvenile *Uromastix*, with their potbellies and clumsy movements, are very cute. Watching them fumble at trying to catch prey, I have seriously wondered how this species has managed to escape extinction. When, after five tries, an animal still fails to bite into a cooled down cricket, the latter has had sufficient time to warm and speed up and thus escape. Still these animals somehow manage to obtain sufficient food because they grow very well.

According to Zwartepoorte (pers. comm.), juveniles are much more insectivorous than their parents are. Blijdorp Zoo feeds them 75% insects and 25% plant matter. I offer my animals insects three times a week (moths or previously cooled down crickets) and, in addition, feed them as much vegetable matter (leafy vegetables, carrots and apples) as they want. The greens as well as the crickets that are fed to juveniles are dusted with large amounts of Korvimin. Under these circumstances, the animals grow relatively quickly. A danger that sometimes occurs when raising juvenile *Uromastix* is constipation. Blijdorp Zoo reports to having lost a number of juveniles to the effects of constipation (ZWARTEPOORTE, 1994).

Zwartepoorte blames the occurrence of constipation on the wrong type of substratum, i.e., sand. However, I think that these animals are confronted with so much sand in their natural environment that they will be able to handle ingesting a small amount of it, without too many deleterious effects. A direct comparison between *U. acanthinura*, which lives on a rocky, clay substratum and '*U. maliensis*' that inhabits sandy areas, is very difficult. I think that the constipation is more likely caused by the lack of a sufficiently hot basking spot (Blijdorp Zoo uses regular light bulbs, while I use halogens). It can be expected that when the animals cannot increase their body temperature to a sufficiently high level to break down hard to digest plant matter that there will be problems. Possibly, the food being too wet may be partly responsible for causing constipation.

Zwartepoorte (pers. comm.) indicates that the young need to be separated at an early age because they are aggressive towards each other. Curalambra (pers. comm.) and Briegoos (pers. comm.) acknowledge the existence of this aggressive behaviour, but report that when the terrarium is equipped with sufficient hiding places and shelters, the juveniles can be kept together. In my experience, it should be possible to rear the young together for at least the first year.

It is striking that the combination that I attempted this year, of juvenile '*U. maliensis*' and juvenile *Uromastix o. ocellata*, was not a good match. The juvenile *maliensis* were extremely aggressive towards the *U. o. ocellata*, but there was no aggression within the same species. This and other observations reported earlier indicate '*Uromastix maliensis*' is a truly different form among the *Uromastix*, and that comparison with other species is not always possible. Still, I have compared them a few times in this article, since it does offer a frame of reference.

SUMMARY

This article describes the Mali *Uromastix*. There are several reasons to use the name *Uromastix maliensis*, although a not entirely convincing argument still stands in the way of the specific recognition of this form. Differences between this and other species are given, as well as a description of the distribution range and habitat of '*U. maliensis*'.

In captivity this species is highly territorial and has a characteristic mating behaviour. Aggression is not uncommon, which may influence whether to keep this species with others. It also affects the size and decoration of the terrarium. Lots of space and hiding places are essential for these animals. Furthermore, high temperatures (33°C air temperature) and lots of light are important, as are shelters with a lower temperature and higher humidity. This species primarily feeds on vegetable matter, especially dandelions, apples and carrots, although animal prey is taken as well. The food is invariably supplemented with a 0.1-1% vitamin-mineral mixture for reptiles. The proper administration of water is still debatable, but I am of the opinion that it can not be harmful to healthy animals to have a bowl of drinking water present in their terrarium. The drinking water is invariably enriched with 12,000 i.u. of vitamin D₃ and 2 gram of calcium lactate per litre. For successful reproduction to occur these animals should hibernate. The duration and purposes of hibernation are discussed. I have opted for a 6-8 week period at a temperature of 20-24°C during the day and 15°C at night. During this period, a small basking light is offered for several hours during the day. Clutch sizes varied from 12-25 eggs, and between 2-24 per clutch hatched.

It is remarkable that three clutches incubated 31-32°C hatched after 110-119 days, whereas two other clutches incubated at 31°C hatched after 87 days. Breeding results depend on the use of UV lights and vitamin D₃ supplements, otherwise the young lack the strength to leave the eggs. Apart from constipation, caused by the lack of sufficiently warm basking spots, rearing the young is relatively problem free. Other diseases that may occur are a worm and bacterial infection and the development of growths.

Male '*Uromastyx maliensis*'.

Photo: G. Hofstra

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